

Open Access Publishing

*Vereist

1. Before you can help the cyborgs to choose a journal in which they can publish, you have to make sure that you know what types of Open Access Publishing there are. Can you refresh your memory and match the type of Open Access publishing to the correct description? Write your answer as: A1, B2... (in alphabetical order) *

A. Preprint	1. A journal that does not publish Open Access, but researchers in the Netherlands may publish their own articles openly in an Open Access repository after 6 months
B. Diamond Open Access	2. A journal that is not Open Access, but that will publish your article Open Access, because your university has a deal with the journal to pay your Article Processing Charges for you
C. Predatory Journal	3. A version of an article that is submitted to an open repository before it is submitted to a journal. This version is usually not formatted, and not peer reviewed. Authors may receive feedback from peers after this submission.
D. Gold Open Access	4. A journal that charges high Article Processing Charges, but does not provide peer review or editing, publishes fraud articles and may not even properly exist
E. Green Open Access	5. A journal that is entirely Open Access – publication costs are covered by funds from an institution, professional association or an external funder

Pick a journal!

The correct descriptions of the Open Access options are below for your convenience

Preprint	A version of an article that is submitted to an open repository before it is submitted to a journal. This version is usually not formatted, and not peer reviewed. Authors may receive feedback from peers after this submission.
Diamond Open Access	A journal that is entirely Open Access – publication costs are covered by funds from an institution, professional association or an external funder
Predatory Journal	A journal that charges high Article Processing Charges, but does not provide peer review or editing, publishes fraud articles and may not even properly exist
Gold Open Access	A journal that is not Open Access, but that will publish your article Open Access, because your university has a deal with the journal to pay your Article Processing Charges for you
Green Open Access	A journal that does not publish Open Access, but researchers in the Netherlands may publish their own articles openly in an Open Access repository after 6 months

2. The cyborgs want to publish their research in a paper and are considering the following options: Cy_buzz, The_borg_nature, INSPIborg, Amazing_cyborg, NEWborg. Try to figure out the ideal order of the journals according to cyborg preferences. Remember that Open Access is not the only criterium for choosing a journal. The first journal is the one most desired. Write your answer as: Cy_buzz, NEWborg, INSPIborg...

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- Cy_buzz is a repository where the cyborgs can publish even if everything else fails.
- NEWborg is completely Open Access. It would be a great fit if publishing in the better-known journals fails and it will be easy to give other cyborgs access to the paper.
- The advantage of publishing in INSPIborg is that it is a well-known journal and cyborgs have a special deal with it – the paper will be made available Open Access upon publication
- The cyborgs are not sure if their paper will be accepted into The_borg_nature. They are also concerned that the paper will not be directly available open access to other cyborgs. The_borg_nature is better known in the borg universe than INSPIborg.
- After talking to other cyborgs it was discovered that Amazing_cyborg doesn't do a peer review and enslaves cyborgs who publish there – to be avoided at all costs
- Cyborgs would prefer green Open Access over gold Open Access to gain maximal attention for their publication

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